

A Review of Use Cases for AI-Native O-RAN

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Abstract—The Radio Access Network (RAN) is evolving to AI-Native, and the Open-RAN (O-RAN) is an important driver for this innovation. This is because O-RAN integrates intelligence with the RAN through the RAN Intelligent Controller RIC component. The RIC leverages machine learning (ML) for a wide variety of use cases, enabling advanced optimization and automation capabilities. This paper presents different use cases where O-RAN is applicable. It also discusses the architectural improvements and challenges of integrating O-RAN into 6G.

Index Terms—Open RAN, O-RAN, RIC, 5G, 6G, AI-Native, use-cases.

I. INTRODUCTION

The technological shift from fifth-generation (5G) to sixth-generation (6G) networks demands dynamic and real-time (RT) control of the network operations. Central to this innovative solution is AI-Native technology, which involves embedding AI into the core fabric of the network. RAN is a key aspect of mobile communication that performs an enormous amount of network operations and demands intelligent control and automation. The O-RAN is currently used in 5G to optimize network operations by incorporating AI as an addition to the RAN. This approach has positively improved the network performance but can only operate at near real-time because of the time-gap in the control loop. So to meet the stringent requirements of 6G, the O-RAN will evolve to be AI-Native, this will ensure network operations are performed and processed at RT. For instance, AI-Native O-RAN can intelligently allocate resources to network slices, such as Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), and Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) at RT ensuring the Service Level Agreements (SLA) of each slice are met.

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A. Motivation and contributions

The importance of O-RAN has led to its gaining traction in the communication network domain, prompting us to conduct a study on this innovative concept that is expected to revolutionize the next-generation network. This research identifies the challenges of implementing AI-Native O-RAN together with relevant architectural enhancements that need to be considered by the RIC to meet the 6G demands.

B. Methodology

A comprehensive method of searching for relevant literature was carried-out with the goal of identifying the use cases of AI-Native O-RAN in future networks. Reputable databases was used for the extraction of literature suitable for the review, the searched databases are Google Scholar, Semantic Scholar, IEEE Xplore, and ResearchGate. The key terms used are “Open RAN”, “O-RAN”, “ORAN”, “Open Radio Access Network”, “O-RAN architecture”, “AI-native O-RAN”, “intelligent O-RAN”, “disaggregated RAN”, “virtualized RAN”, “RAN Intelligent Controller”, “Near-RT RIC”, “Non-RT RIC”, “xApps”, “rApps”. The initial search identified 557 articles and each was subjected to screening based on their abstracts, titles and full-text review. The criteria for inclusion is based on English language publications, which include journal articles and conference papers.

II. USE CASES FOR AI-NATIVE O-RAN

Integrating ML in O-RAN RIC has made a significant revolution in mobile networks, this integration has facilitated diverse range of use cases that aim to enhance network performance, efficiency and reliability for future 6G network. The summary of the AI-Native O-RAN use cases is presented in Table 1.

- Intelligent Traffic Steering: An xApp can dynamically allocate users to appropriate cells, frequencies and radio technologies [7].
- Massive Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (mMIMO) and Beamforming Optimization: rApp can optimize beam configurations while xApp can manage beam tracking and coordinate interference [1].

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF USE CASES FOR AI-NATIVE O-RAN

Use Case	Model	Output	Training data	Action
Massive MIMO Beamforming Optimization [1]	Deep Learning (DL)	Prediction of the MIMO configuration parameters	Calculate Key performance indicators (KPIs) from: coverage, traffic load, and mMIMO.	Apply optimized beam configurations via O1 interface.
Quality of Experience (QoE) Optimization [2]	Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)	Predict traffic type/application and map QoS to QoE.	Simulated traffic pattern and network conditions	Use E2 control or A1 policies to change RAN parameters based on QoE.
Dynamic Spectrum Sharing [3]	DRL	Predict short-term traffic demand from near-RT RAN metrics	Real-world Long-Term Evolution (LTE) traffic data	Control resource configuration and scheduling via E2
RAN slicing [4]	Ape-x based on Deep Q-learning	Predict traffic demand patterns for Network Slice Subnet Instance instances (NSSI) at various times.	UE details and Slice requirements	Reconfigure NSSI attributes via O1 and update Cloud resources via O2.
Handover Management and prediction [5]	Long-short term memory	Customize handover sequences for high-speed UEs.	RSRP (Reference Signal Received Power) , RSRQ (Reference Signal Received Quality), SINR (Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio)	Deploy optimized handover configuration via E2 interface.
Radio Resource Allocation [6]	RL	Optimize radio resource allocation	CIFAR dataset	Deliver radio resource configurations to O-RAN Centralized Unit / O-RAN Distributed Unit (O-CU/O-DU)
Traffic Steering and load balancing [7]	Linear Discriminant Analysis	Selecting the steering policy for different Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) use cases.	Signal strength and network load	Apply traffic management policy via A1 interface to NearRT RIC.

- Network Slicing: xApp can handle inter-slice and intra-slice resource allocation [4].
- Energy Efficiency: The xApp and rApp enable energy saving by adjusting network power dynamically.

III. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Hereby are listed some technical, operational, and regulatory problems that come up when trying to combine O-RAN with 6G.

- Interoperability and standardization: These are major issues as multiple vendors use different methods for implementation. Future RAN components should be thoroughly subjected to testing
- Network management: The complexity of future networks is a major challenge in O-RAN as the RAN components are disaggregated and it demands advanced network automation.
- Scalability: The expansion of future networks is of utmost consideration, more work should be done on developing scalable architecture and framework.

The evolution toward 6G introduces several architectural enhancements.

- **The Real-Time RIC and dApps:** To meet the latency target of future network, it necessitates for the intelligent controllers to be directly embedded in O-CU and O-DU.
- **Unified Data Management and the E3 Interface:** The current O-RAN framework doesn't support user-plane data, the E3 interface is introduced for future networks to bridge the Xapps and rApps with user-plane data for deeper network optimization.
- **Synergy with Large Language Models (LLMs):** Emerging research into "LLM-RIC" frameworks sug-

gests a future where Non-RT RICs use Large Language Models to interpret high-level operator intents [7].

IV. CONCLUSION

The future networks will leverage on AI-Native technology to efficiently optimize network operations for diverse use cases. This innovation in future networks will improve network performance by operating in RT which will improve QoS

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